
POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EFFECTS MEDIA ON AN INDIVIDUAL

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Annotation.

This article discusses the positive and negative effects of media on a person. It is possible to see the influence and pre-influence of these media, their spread, positive or negative effects on people. At present, the main indicator of the use of information media is the fact that information media attract people and get necessary and unnecessary information from it.

Keywords.

Internet, information, phone, computer, positive, negative, person, network, virtual, advertising, interest, tool, motivation, motive, force, teenager.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается положительное и отрицательное влияние СМИ на человека. Можно увидеть влияние и предварительное влияние этих СМИ, их распространение, положительное или отрицательное влияние на людей. В настоящее время основным показателем использования средств массовой информации является то, что средства массовой информации привлекают людей и получают от них нужную и ненужную информацию.

Ключевые слова

Интернет, информация, телефон, компьютер, позитив, негатив, человек, сеть, виртуальный, реклама, интерес, инструмент, мотивация, мотив, сила, подросток.

It is widely known that the use of many media in individuals has increased year after year. The reason for this is that they need and benefit from the media. There are some people who use the news media, enter to benefit, and some advertisements are displayed in front of him, and the person who has seen him begins to be interested. Interest can lead this person into a world of positiveness or, in a negative stream. (Galatians 5:22, 23) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to

answers with you. Because the news media is now being used by young children, teenagers, even those who are not part of a young school period. If their psychology develops with the news media from now on, they will be saved as a book in the early days. More than a book, parents give children a phone, computer, tablet, and a variety of game equipment. No matter how much knowledge a person receives, the word "less" is not enough, for the goal he sets in life leads to the same. Now we're going to look at how you can change your life via social networking site. By means of this knowledge, you can change your life for the better or the worse. Everyone uses social media for different purposes. Just as the human mind, especially the underlying mind, develops, so a person finds his way in the outside world. We must determine for ourselves how to live in life. Because in the future, in this life, we will live on our own. When a person has a child, he is definitely interested in something. When you are using social networks, you should first ask yourself such a question; What's the purpose of me getting into this network? What can I get from here for myself? If you step into the social network, of course, you will be able to find answers to your questions. Once logged in to the social network, you should write less information about yourself, posting less yourself, or your friends, with fewer pictures or video images. Especially religiously, be vigilant because no one knows what purpose your acquaintances will talk to you. People can even find out its nature through the image from his profile. Many people, especially girls, can post a picture of other girls instead of an image of themselves on their profile. Sometimes when it comes to deceiving people, it awakens a different picture of itself. It's worth thinking about meeting those people in real life. This not only makes himself look bad on social media, but also shows that even if he speaks to people in another country, he doesn't have a culture of treating himself.

When we talk to certain people, some of them say, "When I go to social networks I usually deal with good people. But sometimes there will be users whose amazing status, their creations on a topic that sounds relevant to my interest, or images, attract my attention. This encourages me for the better or the worse through my interest. But I don't like this situation because I don't want my life to be in danger.' Dear friends, your interest can reach your own head. We need to be able to renege our interests so that there are no such situations. There are some people who even take pictures with family members or their own wife and publish them on social media. There may also be a situation with a drop in the eye. There are some people who don't respond if strangers turn to it on social media. Girls, on the

other hand, do not make friends with foreign children. And that's because he chose this way for his own safety. Appearance is a lie, it is good to make friends with a person by studying his inner spirituality.

My child says he'll be better than anyone else, he'll read best, he'll get good professions if he's older, but they won't try to do that. It does not attract the necessary attention, does not give the necessary knowledge.

Today, one of the biggest problems in individuals is that it is tied to a needy network and spends the most of its time here. They have no reason, but then they are in a state of shock. First of all, we talk about the positive influence of the mass media on the individual. To be honest, the closest friend of all people, the weapon they need, the tool that passes more time than anyone else is the media, or the Internet. The internet domain is such that I never go online, it's also drawing people who say I don't need it. A person receives the information he needs over the Internet, is likely to be able to find it through this tool, even if he has not found it himself, and others do not. We can see a lot of parental influence through attention and through love. A parent who commands adolescent psychology and determines his or her activities is also responsible, and loading things that affect a teenager well not only when his psychology is progressing can lead to his good and perfect development. In one of Romania's beautiful meanings, The Watch Tower Publications Publications Guide for Jehovah's Witnesses writes: "Keep your house clean as a guest comes and your heart as if you were going to be dead." [2]. Of course, great meaning is hidden in Romania's statements. The cleaner the human heart, the purer it is, the more arrogant it is, the better it will be and as you think. The more powd the heart is, the more a teenager who goes online uses good information and begins to do what has a good conclusion. Social networking, on the other hand, is the same network that determines its entire personality and has a stronger impact on the social environment. We can see some teenagers, and even if they forget the whole world if necessary, this network is pulling it into its domain. They can hear music, documentation, talk, and even talk to people from abroad. Even in our case, the world of the Internet is developing year after year. So, on the other hand, is the need for it. The more people use information exchange, the more information they exchange. There are other purposes, not just sharing information from the media. One of the positive effects is to make contact with other people. If it weren't for the news media, people would spend most of their time on the road. They used to spend money and time bringing one information to a foreign country. To prevent this, social networks and media use it. A person receives and acts on the

information he needs, acquires knowledge, learns information he does not know. The news media entered our era as a great force. Using it, you can take the necessary knowledge and pass through people in all respects, and you can use it in a bad way to move people forward in terms of evil.

And now we're talking about the downsides of the media. First of all, we face the question of whether a person will use it negatively. Of course, there are no people who can negatively benefit from the Internet. This is because it benefits materially in a negative way, or it leads good people in a bad way. The first shot of such people is to invade human psychology and convince themselves. One of the negative aspects is that it reduces a person to a hypnosis state. Because when a person is in a hypnosis state, he cannot understand his psychology, or brain. He does not know what he is doing. It is true that he says that hypnosis is controlled by an infectious person. For example, a person goes online to get the information he needs, and advertising comes out there, or he is interested in checking messages from other sites. At such a time, he is distracted. A distracted person, on the other hand, will have difficulty returning. People's curiosity eats themselves out of this. Through human interest, it can both have the greatest power and not have it. This greatly affects a person. Information broadcast as "news" is often conducted in a biased and spreads her wings. In addition, their thoughts become similarly susceptible. He thinks, he thinks. As a result, that's why it gets caught in the net. There are some information that a person doesn't think is negative or has a big impact on me. On the contrary, he thinks and bets on what he looks like.

One young teenage boy, 14 years old. He could neither be raised nor talked about. To such an extent, he had dived into the phone, the Internet world, that he had not even dealt with family members. It was only with his phone, computer and friends on the Internet. After a long time, all sorts of questions begin to come to him, namely, to make himself look bad to his parents, to separate himself from the outside world, and so on. More and more doubts aroused in the child. That is, from his family, parents, and loved ones. His psychic was changing to such an extent that he nearly even became wild. Years passed, and this boy got caught in a spider web. Threats were made to him by bad people. This boy, on the other hand, was too young to distinguish between white and white, who had not yet seen the world. He doesn't think anything, and he starts doing what the bad guys say. Of course, because he was afraid, he had to do this because he could not do anything. The boy also broke away from his parents and lost his loved ones, and he himself fled to a foreign country. This child was taken to a foreign country by bad people. Excessive

use of the news media and diving into the water eventually lead a person to become insane as well. In conclusion, it should be said that not restricting teenage youth access to the social network, but how social networks form and influence them are causing mental and physical changes in them. This will make our young people feel how they look to the future. Everyone uses the social network for their own benefit. An individual must have comprehensive knowledge to develop himself. When current technology and science are evolving, so does a person. Now, if he acquires good knowledge and acts without distraction, he will certainly achieve his goal. To do this, you first need to do the niat correctly. In his books, Valery Sinelkinov writes: "The cleaner people's intentions are, the more their abilities increase, the more knowledge the universe will have"[3].

THE BIBLE'S VIEWPOINT:

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